

Structural and photophysical templating of conjugated polyelectrolytes with single-stranded DNA

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Section S1: Experimental section

S1.1 Materials and Sample Preparation

Cationic poly(1H-imidazolium,1-methyl-3-[2-[(4-methyl-3-thienyl)oxy]ethyl]-, chloride) (CPT), was synthesised as previously described (Figure 1).^{1,2} It has a molecular weight (M_w) of 22 kDa ($M_n = 11$ kDa), with a polydispersity index (PDI) of 2.0. Each monomer unit of 262.8 g/mol contains one positive charge on the ionic side-chain, compensated by a Cl^- counter ion. Cationic poly[3-(6'-(trimethylphosphonium)hexyl)thiophene-2,5-diyl] (P3HT-PMe₃) and poly[3-(6'-(imidazolium)hexyl)thiophene-2,5-diyl] (P3HT-Im) (Figure 5d) were synthesized as previously described.³ P3HT-PMe₃ and P3HT-Im have number-averaged molecular weight (M_n) of 17.7 kDa and 18.1 kDa (PDI=1.27) and the molecular weight of each monomer unit is 320.01 g/mol and 326.117 g/mol respectively. Each monomer unit is compensated by a Br^- counter ion. A stock solution of each polymer (monomeric concentration of $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M) was prepared in water (purified through a Synergy water purification system) and stored in the freezer. Single-stranded oligonucleotides (ssDNAs) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The ssDNAs with a length of 20 monomers are named dA₂₀, dG₂₀ (homopurine), T406, T406RC, d[(GGAA)₅], d[(TTCC)₅], d[(AT(TAT)₆], d[AT(AAT)₆] (mixed sequence), dT₂₀ and dC₂₀ (homopyrimidine). All oligonucleotides were previously used by Charlebois et al.⁴ and their sequences are listed in the Table S1. A stock solution of each ssDNA (monomeric concentration of $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M) was prepared in water and stored in the freezer. Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) was purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific (catalogue number: 10010-031, pH 7.4, KH₂PO₄ 1.06 mM, Na₂HPO₄ 2.97 mM, NaCl 155 mM) and was used to dilute polymer and ssDNA stock solutions to different monomeric concentrations depending on the experiment: $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M for stationary absorption and CD measurements, $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M for TA and RR experiments in dA₂₀ and T406, and $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M for RR experiments in dC₂₀. For cationic polythiophene/ssDNA experiments, solutions with monomeric equivalence were prepared, with one positive charge from cationic polythiophene for one negative charge of ssDNA in order to have a complete formation of the complex form (see titration in Figure S19).^{2,4} The order of addition for all the solutions was the following: PBS (solvent), cationic polythiophene, ssDNA. We note that the CPT/dC₂₀ complex was formed and studied at 55 °C only for the stationary absorption and CD measurements. In order to avoid precipitation effects during the longer RR and TA measurements, the CPT/dC₂₀ complex was formed and studied at 20 °C, although this decreases the A_{0-0}/A_{0-1} ratio to 1.16 (see Figure S3b).

Table S1: Name, length and sequence of the ssDNAs employed in this study

Name	Length	Sequence (5'-3')
dA₂₀	20	AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
dG₂₀	20	GGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGGG
dC₂₀	20	CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC
dT₂₀	20	TTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTTT
T406	20	CATGATTGAACCATCCACCA
T406RC	20	TGGTGGATGGTTCAATCATG
d[(GGAA)₅]	20	GGAAGGAAGGAAGGAAGGAA
d[(TTCC)₅]	20	TTCCTTCCTTCCTTCCTCC
d[(AT(TAT)₆)]	20	ATTATTATTATTATTATTAT
d[AT(AAT)₆]	20	ATAATAATAATAATAATAAT

For experiments with different lengths of dC, aqueous solutions (0.1 mM, oligomer concentration) of homocytosine of five different lengths (5, 10, 20, 40 and 80 bases) were also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The homocytosine oligomers and their monomeric concentrations are listed in Table S2. PBS was used to dilute the CPT and ssDNA stock solutions. CPT first: 58.4 μL of CPT ($2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M) were added to 1540 μL of PBS to obtain a final concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, on monomeric basis. Then several portions of dC (each portion corresponding to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the total monomeric concentration of CPT) were added to the CPT solution. dC first: a volume of dC stock solution (different for each dC) was added to 1540 μL of PBS to obtain a final concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, on monomeric basis. Then several portions of 14.6 μL of CPT ($2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ M, corresponding to $\frac{1}{4}$ of the total monomeric concentration of dC) were added to the dC solution. After each addition of every titration, the solution was left to equilibrate for at least 5-10 minutes before recording the steady-state absorption and CD spectra. The temperature was set at 20 °C. For the study of the pH dependence of the stability of i-motif conformation for dC₂₀, minor portions of 0.1 M HCl or NaOH were added, either to lower or raise pH respectively. The pH titrations were carried out at 20° C using H₂O, NaCl or PBS buffer as solvent for salt-dependence studies. The reported pH values (measured with accuracy of ± 0.05 pH units) are those obtained before the CD spectra were taken.

Table S2: Name, length, sequence and monomeric concentration of the five homocytosine oligomers employed in this study

Name	Length	Sequence (5'-3')	Monomeric concentration (mM)
dC₅	5	CCCCC	0.5
dC₁₀	10	(CCCCC) ₂	1
dC₂₀	20	(CCCCC) ₄	2
dC₄₀	40	(CCCCC) ₈	4
dC₈₀	80	(CCCCC) ₁₆	8

S1.2 Experimental details

Absorption spectroscopy. Absorption spectra were recorded with a UV/VIS/NIR Lambda 900 spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer). A quartz cuvette with an optical path length of 10 mm was placed inside the stand-alone Peltier-based temperature-controlled cuvette holder (Flash300/E, Quantum Northwest) and the temperature was allowed to stabilize for 5-10 min. A small magnetic stir bar was placed in the cuvette and the stirring speed could be controlled with the cuvette holder.

Circular Dichroism spectroscopy. CD spectra were recorded with a J-715 spectropolarimeter (Jasco). A quartz cuvette with an optical path length of 10 mm was placed inside the temperature-controlled holder of the spectropolarimeter. For the pH titration of dC₂₀, CD spectra were recorded with a Jasco J-815 CD Spectrometer using EPR suprasil tubes (diameter: 4 mm).

Transient Absorption Spectroscopy. TA spectra were recorded using femtosecond pulsed laser pump-probe spectroscopy. The solutions were placed in a quartz cuvette with an optical path length of 2 mm (Starna Cells Inc.) placed inside the temperature-controlled holder and held by a piece of aluminium. Pump excitation at 400 nm (200 fs resolution) was achieved by frequency doubling the fundamental 800 nm laser output (from a Ti:sapphire laser system with regenerative amplification providing 35 fs pulses at a repetition rate of 1 kHz, Astrella, Coherent). As an alternative, an excitation beam at 580 nm (<100 fs resolution) was generated with a commercial optical parametric amplifier (OPerA Solo, Coherent). The pump diameter was about 1 mm and the pump intensity was 400 nJ with the 400 nm excitation and between 200-330 nJ for the 580 nm excitation. The probe beam consisted of a white light continuum (~450-1200 nm) generated by passing a portion of the 800 nm amplified Ti:sapphire output through a 5 mm thick sapphire

window. Either 720 nm low pass filters or 850 nm long pass filters were used to remove the remaining fundamental intensity from the white light, when the visible and the near-infrared (nIR) parts of the spectrum were recorded separately. The probe intensity was negligible compared to the pump intensity and the spot size was much smaller (probe energy of < 5 nJ, probe diameter of about 160 μm). The probe pulses were time-delayed with respect to the pump pulses by means of a computer-controlled translation stage. The probe beam was split before the sample into a signal beam (transmitted through the sample and overlapped with the pump beam) and a reference beam. The signal and reference beams were detected separately using a pair of spectrographs (home-built prism spectrometers) equipped with 512 x 58 pixels back-thinned CCDs (Hamamatsu S07030-0906) and assembled by Entwicklungsbüro Stresing, Berlin. The pump beam was chopped at half the amplifier frequency to improve the sensitivity of the set-up. The transmitted intensity of the signal beam was recorded shot-by-shot and it was corrected for laser intensity fluctuations using the reference beam. The single shot TA spectra were averaged 3000 times at each time delay and the entire range of measured time delays (between -4 ps and 1 ns) was scanned 5 times, without any noticeable signs of degradation. Wavelength calibration was accomplished with a series of 10 nm bandpass filters. To avoid polarization effects, the relative polarization of the probe and pump pulses was set at the magic angle. All spectra were corrected for the chirp of the white-light probe. MATLAB and IgorPro software were used for data analysis.

Resonance Raman Studies. Resonance Raman (RR) spectra of cationic polythiophene/ssDNA complexes were obtained with excitation at 435.69, 473, 532 and 266 nm. The 532 and 266 nm excitation wavelengths employed in the RR experiments were provided by the second and fourth harmonics of a Q-switched Nd:YAG laser (PRO-230, 30 Hz, Spectra Physics) and the 435.69 nm was produced via Raman shifting at 532 nm in a 1 m tube containing H₂ gas. The 473 nm excitation was obtained from a CW diode laser (Ultralasers, 50 mW OEM DPSS Laser). The excitation light was focused into a spinning cell consisting of an EPR suprasil tube (diameter: 4 mm) attached to a rheostat-controlled motor for choice of rotation speed. Use of the spinning cell prolonged the lifetime of the samples. Modest excitation energies (2.1 mW at 473 nm and 435.69 nm, 0.1 mW (3.3 μJ per pulse) at 532 nm, and 0.07 mW at 266 nm (~2.5 μJ per pulse)) were employed to avoid decomposition of the sample, which was monitored by obtaining the absorption spectrum of the sample before and after exposure. The Raman scattered light was collected in a backscattering geometry and delivered to a 0.75m focal-length Czerny–Turner spectrograph, equipped with a

1200-grooves/mm holographic grating for the visible wavelengths and a 2400 grooves/mm holographic grating for excitation at 266 nm. The slit width was set to 100 μm providing for 5 cm^{-1} spectral resolution at the visible wavelengths used in this work and 7 cm^{-1} at 266 nm. The scattered light was detected by a LN_2 -cooled 2048 x 512 pixel, back-illuminated UV-enhanced CCD detector (Spec10:2KBUV/LN, Princeton Instruments). Each spectrum with excitation in the visible is the accumulation of 6 \times 5 min spectra, while 20 \times 10 min spectra were required in the UV. Frequency calibration of the spectra was accomplished with the use of cyclohexane. MATLAB and ORIGIN software were used for spectral treatment and analysis.

Section S2: MD simulations

For the ssDNA fragments only, the system featured the respective ssDNA 20mer (dC₂₀ or dA₂₀), approximately 5000 water molecules and 20 Na⁺ counter ions for charge neutralization. The parmbsc1 force field^{5,6} was used for ssDNA, while water was modelled with the TIP3P⁷ force field with corresponding parameters for Na⁺ ions.⁸ Both systems were first equilibrated at 300 K and 1 atm, and then the production phase was carried out for a total of 1.8 μ s, with a time step of 2 fs. Bonds involving H atoms were kept fixed using the SHAKE algorithm.

For all CPT/ssDNA assemblies, two separate simulations were performed for each system with different initial distances between the ssDNA and the polymer (10 Å and 30 Å, respectively). The resulting periodic boxes contained approximately 30000 and 54000 water molecules, respectively. In addition to the solvent and the ssDNA and CPT 20mers, the system setup for both simulations also included a biologically relevant 150 mM concentration of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions, in line with the ionic strength of the PBS buffer solution employed in the experiments. The ssDNA 20mers, water and ions were described in the same fashion as in the pure ssDNA simulations. Point charges for the polymer atoms (listed in detail in Figure S1 and Tables S3-S4) were obtained from static calculations performed on CPT tetramers, using Gaussian09,⁹ and the polarizable continuum model for water.^{10,11} The geometry of the tetramers was optimized at the Density Functional Theory (DFT) level;^{12,13} employing the B3LYP functional^{14,15} combined with the 6-31G(d,p) basis set,^{16,17} recently used for a study of another polythiophene derivative.¹⁸ Atom types and interactions between CPT atoms were assigned according to the recently updated General AMBER force field (GAFF2)^{19,20} with the exception of the S-C-C-S torsion angle where parameters were selected from reference.¹⁸ The simulation protocol was the same as for the pure ssDNA simulations, with the production phase amounting to a total of 1.54 μ s from the two independent MD runs. All simulations were carried out with the GPU version of AMBER16.²¹

A simulation for CPT in aqueous solution (with approximately 25000 water molecules and 150 mM NaCl) was also carried out. The aforementioned parametrization for CPT, H₂O, Na⁺ and Cl⁻ was used. The simulation protocol used for the DNA and CPT/DNA systems was also employed here, amounting to 1.5 μ s of total simulation time in the production phase.

Chirality analysis: For two neighboring nucleobases, i and $i+1$, their local chirality index, $CI_{i,i+1}$, is defined as :

$$CI_{i,i+1} = \frac{\vec{r}_{i,i+1} \cdot (\vec{\mu}_i \times \vec{\mu}_{i+1})}{|\vec{r}_{i,i+1}| \cdot |\vec{\mu}_i| \cdot |\vec{\mu}_{i+1}|} \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $\vec{r}_{i,i+1}$ is the vector connecting the centres of mass of the nucleobases i and $i+1$, while $\vec{\mu}_i$ and $\vec{\mu}_{i+1}$ are unit vectors that are perpendicular to their respective planes. The average local chirality index for a given frame of the trajectory is then obtained by averaging the indices over the entire length of the ssDNA.

Point charges of the CPT monomer

Figure S1. Depiction of a CPT monomer. Atom labels correspond to those in Tables S3 and S4, where the effective atomic point charges of the CPT monomer are presented.

Table S3. Point charges of CPT monomer in the middle of the CPT sequence.

atom index	atom species	Charge	atom index	atom species	charge
1	S	-0.0567	15	H	0.1537
2	C	-0.0030	16	H	0.1537
3	C	-0.0525	17	N	0.1458
4	C	0.0288	18	C	-0.1902
5	C	0.1232	19	H	0.2505
6	C	-0.3312	20	C	-0.1985
7	H	0.1129	21	H	0.2463
8	H	0.1129	22	C	-0.0540
9	H	0.1129	23	H	0.2128
10	O	-0.2246	24	N	0.2436
11	C	0.0582	25	C	-0.3803
12	H	0.0949	26	H	0.1781
13	H	0.0949	27	H	0.1781
14	C	-0.1884	28	H	0.1781

Table S4. Point charges of terminal CPT monomer (with atom 2 capped with a hydrogen atom). Index 29 corresponds to the capping hydrogen.

atom index	atom species	Charge	atom index	atom species	charge
1	S	-0.0070	16	H	0.1461
2	C	-0.3323	17	N	0.1477
3	C	-0.0840	18	C	-0.1490
4	C	0.0981	19	H	0.2266
5	C	0.1799	20	C	-0.2256
6	C	-0.3333	21	H	0.2405
7	H	0.1044	22	C	-0.0909
8	H	0.1044	23	H	0.2165
9	H	0.1044	24	N	0.2690
10	O	-0.2784	25	C	-0.3854
11	C	0.2748	26	H	0.1787
12	H	0.0304	27	H	0.1787
13	H	0.0304	28	H	0.1787
14	C	-0.2064	29	H	0.2368
15	H	0.1461			

Section S3: Optical response of CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀

S3.1 Absorption and CD spectroscopy

S3.1.1 CPT/dA₂₀ temperature stability

Figure S2. Absorption and CD spectra of CPT/dA₂₀ in PBS at 20 and 55 °C and CD spectrum of CPT at 20 °C. Concentration of each component is $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis).

In Figure S2, the absorption and CD spectra of CPT/dA₂₀ at 20 and 55 °C are presented. With increasing temperature, the polymer absorption band blue-shifts. This trend is similar to what was observed for CPT alone in solution²² with the polymer chains becoming more random coiled at high temperature. The (+/-) CD signal centred at 543 nm present for CPT/dA₂₀ at 20 °C disappears at 55 °C. This illustrates that the complex is unstable and is disrupted since CPT (achiral molecule) has no CD signal when alone.

S3.1.2 CPT/dC₂₀ temperature stability

Figure S3. (a) Normalised absorption spectra of CPT/dC₂₀ in PBS formed at 55 °C and then the temperature was varied to 20 and 5 °C. (b) Absorption spectra (y-axis expressed in extinction coefficient) of CPT/dC₂₀ formed at 55 °C and at 20 °C. Concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis).

Figure S3a shows the normalised absorption spectra for CPT/dC₂₀ formed at 55 °C with a subsequent variation in the solution temperature from 55 to 20 and 5 °C. The three spectra are almost identical showing distinct vibronic peaks with the 0-0 transition at 594 nm (corresponding to the maximum absorbance), the 0-1 at 547 nm, the 0-2 at 510 nm and the 0-3 at around 470 nm. Therefore, the temperature has no influence on the complex once is formed, suggesting that CPT/dC₂₀ is more stable compared to CPT/dA₂₀. Figure S3b shows the spectra of CPT/dC₂₀ formed at two different temperatures, 55 and 20 °C. Even though the shape of the absorption is quite similar, the complex formed at 55 °C is slightly more structured compared to the complex formed at 20 °C, with a considerably higher A₀₋₀/A₀₋₁ ratio (1.24 vs 1.16). As the CPT conformation is very sensitive to temperature,²² its starting temperature influences the final conformation in the complex form, with the highest templating effect of dC₂₀ at 55 °C.

S3.1.3 pH titration and salt-dependence of dC₂₀ conformation

Figure S4. CD (top) and absorption spectra (bottom) of (a) pH titration of dC₂₀ in PBS buffer and (b) at pH 7.3 in H₂O, NaCl and PBS buffer with calculation of the fraction of i-motif adopted by dC₂₀.

S3.2 Conformation of dA_{20} and dC_{20} from MD simulations

Figure S5. Representative structures of single-stranded dA_{20} (a) and dC_{20} (b and c) fragments. Phosphorus atoms are in dark yellow, carbons in green, hydrogens in white, nitrogens in blue, and oxygens in red color.

S3.3 CD Spectra of dA_{20} and dC_{20} from MD simulations

Figure S6. Experimental (left axis) and theoretical (right axis) CD spectra of dA_{20} alone and CPT/ dA_{20} (top) and dC_{20} alone and CPT/ dC_{20} (bottom).

Figure S6 shows the CD spectra that were computed for the ssDNAs from our MD structures, both alone and in complex with CPT. The calculation of the CD spectra was performed with the online interface DichroCalc, developed in the group of Jonathan Hirst²³. To ensure that convergence is reached, the calculation of the CD spectra was carried out for both 10 and 20 MD structures in each of the four cases and the average CD spectra of the two independent simulations are presented. The calculated CD signal reproduces the experimental results, thus showing that the MD structures are consistent with the CD experiments in terms of DNA conformation. In the case of dA_{20} we obtained a positive/negative/positive signal at ~ 250 nm, ~ 235 nm and ~ 200 nm, respectively, with similar relative intensities as in the experimental CD spectrum. Similarly, in the case of dC_{20} , the +/- bisignate signal at ~ 290 and 270 nm resembles the experimental signal.

Section S4: Backbone planarity of CPT in the complexes with dA₂₀ and dC₂₀

S4.1 Visible Resonance Raman

Figure S7. RR spectra normalized with respect to the intensity of the band at ~ 1487 cm^{-1} with excitation at 435.69 nm for CPT/dT₂₀, 473 nm for CPT/dA₂₀, CPT/T406 and CPT/dC₂₀ and 532 nm for CPT/dC₂₀, all in PBS buffer with a concentration of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M (monomeric basis) at room temperature. The spectra are shown over an extended range compared to the main text, in order to show the low frequency modes between 800-1000 cm^{-1} . These modes are greatly enhanced in the case of CPT/dC₂₀.

Figure S7 shows that the most intense bands appear around 1400, 1450 and 1488 cm^{-1} and are associated with the mixed $\text{C}_\alpha\text{-C}_\alpha'$ and $\text{C}_\beta\text{-C}_\beta'$, $\text{C}_\alpha=\text{C}_\beta(\text{O})$ and $\text{C}_\alpha=\text{C}_\beta(\text{Me})$ ring stretching vibrations, respectively, according to our previous DFT calculations (see Table S5).²² A sharper band ~ 1460 cm^{-1} in the CPT/dC₂₀ spectrum suggested that another band contributes to the broadening of the transitions between 1430 and 1550 cm^{-1} , confirmed by deconvolution of the spectra (see Figure S8), and assigned to the $\text{C}_\alpha=\text{C}_\beta(\text{Me})$ ring symmetric stretch. A weak shoulder around 1520 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\text{C}_\alpha=\text{C}_\beta$ asymmetric stretch.

Figure S8. Deconvolution of RR spectra for (a) CPT/dA₂₀ (b) CPT/T406 (c) CPT/dC₂₀ with excitation at 473 nm and (d) CPT/dC₂₀ with excitation at 532 nm.

Table S5. Comparison of the frequencies (cm^{-1}) of RR bands of pure CPT in various complexes.

Frequency (cm^{-1})					Assignment
CPT	CPT/dA ₂₀	CPT/T406	CPT/dC ₂₀ $\lambda_{exc} = 473 \text{ nm}$	CPT/dC ₂₀ $\lambda_{exc} = 532 \text{ nm}$	
1376	1378	1378	1376	1376	Mixed C _{β} -C _{β'} and C _{α} -C _{α'} stretching
1400	1400	1399	1397	1394	Mixed C _{β} -C _{β'} and C _{α} -C _{α'} stretching
1449	1448	1448	1448	1448	C _{α} =C _{β} (O) ring stretching
1464	1465	1468	1464	1463	C _{α} =C _{β} (Me) ring stretching
1487	1486	1487	1484	1484	C _{α} =C _{β} (Me) ring stretching
1514	1518	1512	1510	1510	C _{α} -C _{β} ring stretching (anti)

S4.2 Dihedral angles between thiophene rings from MD simulations

Figure S9. Distributions of the S-C-C-S dihedral angle between the adjacent thiophene rings in CPT alone and assembled with dA₂₀ and dC₂₀.

Section S5: Atomistic-level details of the CPT/ssDNA interactions

S5.1 UV Resonance Raman spectroscopy

Figure S10. UVRR spectra of (a) dA₂₀ and CPT/dA₂₀ (b) T406 and CPT/T406 in PBS buffer with a concentration of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M and (c) dC₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ in PBS buffer with a concentration of $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M (monomeric basis) at room temperature with excitation at 266 nm. The spectra are shown over an extended range compared to the main text. Structure of the deoxyribonucleotides of (d) adenine and (e) cytosine in which the glycosidic torsional angle χ is depicted, defined by O4'-C1'-N9-C8 atoms for deoxyadenosine and O4'-C1'-N1-C6 atoms for deoxycytidine.

Figure S10 presents the UVRR spectra of the various ssDNAs and their complexes with CPT showing the lower frequency region. Additional bands observed in the range of 800-1150 cm^{-1} are assigned to vibrations originating from the quartz cell, which could not be fully subtracted. The assignment of the dominant bands of ssDNA can be found in Table S6. Raman bands in the dA₂₀ spectrum (Figure S10a) appearing at 1309, 1338, 1425 and 1482 cm^{-1} are assigned primarily to vibrations localized at the C8 end of adenine while those that appear at 1581 and 1604 cm^{-1} are attributed to the triene system C2=N3-C4=C5-N7=C8 and NH₂ scissoring mode, respectively. Characteristic bands of dC₂₀ (Figure S10c) that correspond to the enamine fragment C6=C5-C4=N3 along with the exocyclic C4-NH₂ are found at 784, 1246, 1297, 1381 and 1532 cm^{-1} . Additional bands are attributed to the vibrational modes of NH₂ and are seen at 991 and 1618 cm^{-1} . Finally, a band assigned to the stretching mode of C2=O is found at 1656 cm^{-1} .

The dashed lines are used for the illustration of any shifts or differences in intensity between the spectra of oligonucleotides alone and the spectra of the respective complexes. In dA₂₀ and CPT/dA₂₀ spectra (Figure S10a) as well as in T406 and CPT/T406 (Figure S10b) spectra no changes are observed, in contrast to the case of the dC₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ spectra (Figure S10c) for which significant changes are observed in the band intensities at 991, 1297, 1381 and 1532 cm^{-1} . In addition, the dashed lines help indicate in the case of the T406 spectra which bands correspond to adenine and which to cytosine. As a result, the similarity between the dA₂₀ and T406 spectra is illustrated, as most of the bands in T406 spectra correspond to adenine, overlapping most of the bands attributed to cytosine due to greater resonance enhancement.

Table S6. Frequencies (cm^{-1}) and assignments of dominant RR bands in UVRR spectra of ssDNA

dA ₂₀		dC ₂₀		T406	
Frequency (cm^{-1})	Assignment ¹	Frequency (cm^{-1})	Assignment	Frequency (cm^{-1})	Assignment
1258	N1C6, C6N6	1246	δ C6H, C4N4	1246	A: N1C6, C6N6 C: δ C6H, C4N4
1309	N9C8, N3C2, δ C8H, δ C2H	1297	N1C6, C5C6	1304	A: N9C8, N3C2, δ C8H, δ C2H
1338	N7C5, C8N7	1381	C4N4, N1C2	1334	A: N7C5, C8N7
1377	C1N9, C6N6	1532	N3C4, N1C2	1373	C: C4N4, N1C2 A: C1N9, C6N6
1425	C4N9, δ C8H	1618	δ NH ₂ , C4N4	1423	A: C4N9, δ C8H
1484	δ C2H, N9C8, δ C8H	1656	C2O, C2N3	1483	A: δ C2H, N9C8, δ C8H
1506	N7C8			1506	A: N7C8
1581	C5C4, C4N3			1527	C: N3C4, N1C2
1603	δ NH ₂ , C5C6, C6N6			1579	A: C5C4, C4N3 G: C4N3, C5C4, N7C5
				1609	A: δ NH ₂ , C5C6, C6N6
				1650	C: C2O, C2N3

¹ Stretching vibrations, unless denoted δ (bending vibrations)

S5.2 Electrostatic interactions from MD simulations

In a next step, the abundance of electrostatic interactions between negatively charged phosphate groups of DNA nucleotides and positively charged imidazole rings of CPT was compared for the CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ assemblies. More precisely, a close contact analysis was performed, in order to identify the fraction of the total simulation time during which the phosphate group of each DNA nucleotide was in close proximity to the cationic imidazole of any CPT monomer. An atom-atom threshold distance of 2.5 Å was employed in this analysis. The detailed outcome, displaying the occupancy fraction for all 20 adenines in CPT/dA₂₀ and for all 20 cytosines in CPT/dC₂₀ is available in the histogram of Figure S11.

Figure S11. Analysis of close contacts between the DNA and CPT units in CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀.

Regarding CPT/dA₂₀, the results suggest that the phosphate groups of 5 adenine nucleotides are actively involved in interactions with imidazole rings (with occupation fractions greater than 20%, one even up to 36%). In CPT/dC₂₀, two cytosine nucleotides are strongly involved in electrostatic interactions with CPT (occupancy greater than 40%), while four more also contribute significantly (fraction of at least 20%). The outcome is very similar for CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀.

To better assess this, the number of PO₄-imidazole interactions over the course of the MD trajectories were determined for both CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ (using again an atom-atom threshold distance of 2.5 Å). The time series of these interactions are shown in Figure S12 and the corresponding histograms are displayed in Figure S13.

Figure S12. Number of interactions observed for CPT/dA₂₀ (blue color) and CPT/dC₂₀ (green color) along the MD trajectories. Frames 1-42000 correspond to the first trajectory, while frames 42001-77000 to the second trajectory.

Figure S13. Probability distribution of the number of electrostatic interactions for CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ assemblies.

As Figure S13 shows, structures with 0 to 2 electrostatic interactions are more frequently encountered for CPT/dA₂₀ than for CPT/dC₂₀. For higher numbers of interactions, the corresponding fractions are instead larger for CPT/dC₂₀.

Figure S14. Close contacts between the phosphate groups of dC₂₀ and the imidazole rings from the CPT side chain.

S5.3 Stacking Interactions from MD simulations

In addition to electrostatic interactions, stacking interactions can play an important role. To quantify the extent of stacking, we also performed a close contact analysis for all possible stacking combinations: base-thiophene, base-imidazole, base-base (intra-DNA) and thiophene-imidazole (intra-CPT). The analysis was carried out using the centre of mass of each ring, and a threshold distance of 4.5 Å (which excludes T-shape conformations) for assessing whether two rings are stacked. The results of this analysis are displayed in the histograms of Figures S15.1-S15.5.

Figure S15.1. Analysis of stacking interactions between DNA bases and thiophene rings: Fraction of the entire simulation time during which each adenine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with a thiophene in CPT/dA₂₀ (blue color), and each cytosine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with a thiophene in CPT/dC₂₀ (red color).

Figure S15.2. Analysis of stacking interactions between DNA bases and CPT imidazole rings: Fraction of the entire simulation time during which each adenine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with an imidazole in CPT/dA₂₀ (blue color), and each cytosine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with an imidazole in CPT/dC₂₀ (red color).

Figure S15.3. Analysis of intra-DNA stacking interactions in dA₂₀: Fraction of the entire simulation time during which each adenine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with another adenine in dA₂₀ alone (blue color) and in CPT/dA₂₀ (red color).

Figure S15.4. Analysis of intra-DNA stacking interactions in dC₂₀: Fraction of the entire simulation time during which each cytosine is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with another cytosine in dC₂₀ alone (blue color) and in CPT/dC₂₀ (red color).

Figure S15.5. Analysis of intra-CPT stacking interactions: Fraction of the entire simulation time during which each thiophene is involved in a π - π stacking interaction with an imidazole in CPT/dA₂₀ (blue color) and in CPT/dC₂₀ (red color).

Figure S15.1 shows that stacking of cytosines with thiophenes within CPT/dC₂₀ occurs much more frequently than adenine-thiophene stacking within CPT/dA₂₀: In CPT/dC₂₀, five cytosines are involved in stacking interactions with thiophenes for $\geq 50\%$ of the total simulation time, while two more Cs are stacked against thiophenes for $\geq 40\%$ of the MD time. In contrast, only three adenines of CPT/dA₂₀ are involved in stacking with a thiophene for $\geq 40\%$ of the trajectory. In addition, a total of 15 cytosines are involved in stacking interactions with thiophenes in CPT/dC₂₀, as opposed to only 7 adenines in CPT/dA₂₀. Figure S15.2 demonstrates that stacking in CPT/dC₂₀ also occurs between cytosines and imidazole rings, and again is much less frequently observed in CPT/dA₂₀.

This analysis demonstrates that conformational differences in CPT/dA₂₀ vs CPT/dC₂₀ are strongly related to the different extent of interchain stacking within each complex. The ability of cytosine to stack against thiophene/imidazole rings strongly contributes to the more compact structure adopted by CPT/dC₂₀, while the far more limited stacking observed between adenines and CPT rings leads to a much looser structure for CPT/dA₂₀.

Figure S15.3 shows that the intra-stacking within dA₂₀ remains – as expected – practically unaffected in the presence or absence of CPT. A decrease upon the addition of the polymer is only observed for adenine 6, in line with the observation that dA₂₀ in CPT/dA₂₀ is composed of two helices comprising the first 5 and last 15 residues, respectively (see manuscript). In contrast, intra-DNA stacking is decreased for dC₂₀ when CPT is added (Figure S15.4), which can also be anticipated, given the involvement of C bases in π - π stacking interactions with thiophene and imidazole rings. Finally, the picture on stacking interactions is completed with a comparison of intra-CPT stacking in CPT/dA₂₀ vs CPT/dC₂₀ (Figure S15.5). Such thiophene-imidazole interactions are more common in CPT/dA₂₀. This is also expected, as interchain π - π stacking is limited in CPT/dA₂₀, thus favoring interactions between free thiophenes and imidazoles.

S5.4 Hydrogen Bonding from MD simulations

S5.4.1 Hydrogen bonds in ssDNA alone

In order to quantify the difference in hydrogen bonding between dA₂₀ and dC₂₀, the respective plugin for VMD was used. Cutoff criteria included thresholds of 3.0 Å for the donor-acceptor distance and 20° for the hydrogen-donor-acceptor angle. The probability distributions of the number of hydrogen bonds (H-bonds) for the two ssDNA fragments are depicted in Figure S16. The distribution of dA₂₀ is characterized by a peak at 0 H-bonds, and then steeply declines to a probability of 0 as the number of H-bonds increases. On the other hand, the distribution of dC₂₀ shows that structures with varying number of H-bonds are frequently visited, further highlighting the flexibility of this fragment.

Figure S16. Probability distribution of the number of hydrogen bonds for ssDNA fragments.

Figure S17. Hydrogen bonding interactions between the NH_2 group of cytosine with the phosphate backbone.

S5.4.2 Hydrogen bonds in CPT/ssDNA

The number of H-bonds observed along the trajectories of CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ was monitored (Figure S18). Hydrogen bonds between ssDNA units were determined using the same distance and angle criteria as for pure ssDNA (3.0 Å and 20°, respectively). On the contrary, looser criteria (distance of 3.5 Å and angle of 40°) were applied for the H-bonds between ssDNA and CPT monomers.

Figure S18. Number of hydrogen bonds observed for (a) CPT/dA₂₀ and (b) CPT/dC₂₀ along the MD trajectories. DNA-DNA (green color) and CPT-DNA (blue color) hydrogen bonds are shown separately. For each system, frames 1-42000 and 42001-77000 correspond to the first and the second independent simulation, respectively.

S5.5 Chalcogen Bonding Interactions

The potential contribution of chalcogen bonds between the sulfur (S) atom of thiophenes and the oxygens of the CPT side chains to the structure adopted by the polymer chain was also investigated. To quantify the strength of such interactions for the system under study, static DFT calculations of a representative model system (thiophene and dimethyl ether) were carried out, varying the S--O distance between 2 and 5 Å. We performed this protocol for two initial configurations, differing in the thiophene-ether orientation. The procedure was carried out both in the gas phase and with an implicit solvation model (polarizable continuum model – PCM), with the B3LYP functional and the 6-31++G* basis set. In both cases, the curve of the interaction energy vs the S--O distance was very smooth, with an extremely shallow energy minimum of less than 0.4 kcal/mol binding energy at ca. 3.8 - 4.0 Å. Representative graphs are reported in Figure S19 (implicit solvation).

Figure S19. The interaction energy between a thiophene monomer and a dimethyl ether as a function of the distance between the thiophene sulfur and ether oxygen atoms, determined from static DFT calculations with the B3LYP functional, under implicit solvation (water, PCM model). Graphs are shown for two different thiophene-ether configurations (described in the respective legends).

These characteristics demonstrate that S--O interactions are very weak for the model system, and therefore for CPT as well. They thus seem to have no decisive effect on the structure of the CPT polymer considered in the present study. In the context of the classical MD simulations performed in this work, this outcome shows that GAFF2 force field – while not polarizable and not explicitly accounting for the anisotropic electron density distribution on the sulfur atom, i.e. cannot capture chalcogen bonding – is fully appropriate for describing CPT at an atomistic level.

Section S6: Effect of dC length on CPT/dC complex formation

S6.1 Absorption and CD titration

Figure S20. Absorption and CD spectra of CPT with different relative amounts of (a) dC₅, (b) dC₁₀, (c) dC₂₀, (d) dC₄₀ and (e) dC₈₀. All solutions were in PBS buffer with a CPT concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis), 25 °C. The relative amount of oligomer is referred to the monomeric concentration of the DNA bases with respect to the CPT one.

Figure S20 shows that the best templating ability is achieved with a monomeric equivalence (1:1) between CPT and dCs with length larger than 5 bases, leading to the highest A_{0-0}/A_{0-1} ratio for each CPT/dC complex (Table S7). The overall absorption amplitude of 1:1 mixtures exhibits slightly lower intensity due to partial precipitation occurring in the experiment time, which also causes some scattering (absorption above 660 nm). In order to better compare the formed complexes, these spectra are slightly scaled in order to compensate for the overall signal decrease. In contrast to dC₁₀-dC₈₀, dC₅ maximizes the templating effect on CPT when 2.25 equivalents are added (2.25 cytosine monomers for 1 thiophene unit).

The shape of the induced CD signal of CPT in the different CPT/dC complexes between 450 nm and 670 nm is the result of the superposition of several distinct (-/+) CD signals, one for each vibronic peak.

Table S7. A_{0-0}/A_{0-1} ratio for the different CPT/dC complexes.

CPT/Oligocytosine	A_{0-0}/A_{0-1}
CPT/dC ₅ (1:1)	0.83
CPT/dC ₅ (1:2.25)	1.17
CPT/dC ₅ (1:2.25, after 1 day)	1.27
CPT/dC ₁₀ (1:1)	1.19
CPT/dC ₂₀ (1:1)	1.16
CPT/dC ₄₀ (1:1)	1.12
CPT/dC ₈₀ (1:1)	1.06

In the 220-320 nm spectral region (Figure S21), we can observe that the shape of the CD signal varies between the longer (≥ 20) and shorter dC's in the absence of the polymer, meaning that the ssDNAs are found in different conformations prior to complexation, especially in the case of dC₅. Longer chains (dC₄₀, dC₈₀) form secondary structures that do not completely unfold upon interaction with CPT, thus part of the DNA does not complex with CPT and remains in its initial

secondary structure, producing a similar signal but with reduced ellipticity, while the entire CPT can be templated (note that cytosines stack with every other thiophene as explained in the main text). However, this signal is different than the one produced in the case of complexes with dC₁₀ and dC₂₀, where the entire oligonucleotide is involved in the complex, assuming a different conformation as also confirmed from our MD simulations and the UVRR data. Therefore, the similarity in the CD signal in the visible (Figure S22) and the difference in the UV for these complexes are not incompatible. dC₅ is a different case, which is already in a different conformation prior to complexation, since the short length does not allow for higher order structures. The CD signal in this case remains similar after complexation, and not too different from the spectrum for dC₁₀ after complexation (except slightly shifted).

Figure S21. CD spectra of the different dCs (solid lines) and the corresponding CPT/dC complexes (dashed lines) in PBS at 20 °C. The spectra are zoomed in the UV region to show the CD signals that are mainly from dCs (even though an induced CD signal from CPT and possible coupling or charge transfer to the ssDNA cannot be completely excluded). Concentration: $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis of cytosine bases for dCs alone and of CPT for CPT/dCs).

Figure S22. CD spectra of the different CPT/dC complexes in PBS at 20 °C. The spectra are zoomed in the visible region to show the CD signals that are attributed to CPT. Concentration: $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis of cytosine bases for dCs and of CPT for CPT/dCs).

Figure S23. (a) Absorption spectra of CPT/dC₅ (4:9) recorded 10 minutes after addition of the last dC₅ portion and after 1 day (after shaking to redissolve the precipitate formed in the meantime). (b) Normalized CD signal as a function of the dC equivalents titrated in CPT solution for the various dC lengths. The x axis has been shifted relative to the position of 50% CD signal.

Figure S23(b) shows a plot of the normalized CD signal at 604 nm as a function of dC concentration for the various dC lengths. We observe differences in the slope of the sigmoidal curve as a function of dC length, alluding to a change in the cooperativity of the system, which can explain the slower complex formation in the case of dC₅.

Figure S24. Absorption and CD spectra of (a) dC₅ and (b) dC₁₀ with different relative amounts of CPT (in PBS buffer with a dC concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M, monomeric basis, 20 °C). The scaled absorption spectrum of CPT alone is added as reference (dashed grey line).

Section S7: Generalization to other ssDNA and polythiophene systems

In the optical response, CPT/T406 shows a somewhat intermediate behaviour between the one of the CPT complexes with dA₂₀ and dC₂₀ (Figure 2a, b). The absorption band of the CPT π - π^* transition becomes slightly structured, with the 0-0 vibronic transition at 555 nm and the 0-1 transition at 522 nm, corresponding to the wavelength of maximum absorbance. The vibronic progression shows that the polymer in the CPT/T406 complex is in a more ordered conformation compared to CPT/dA₂₀. CPT/T406 has a (+/-) CD signal centred at 520 nm, indicating that like dA₂₀, T406 induces chirality in CPT with a preferential right-handed helical conformation.²⁴ Nevertheless, in this case, the supramolecular assembly is more rigid because the CD signal in the visible region is maintained even at 55 °C and the absorption undergoes minor changes (see Figure S26). The UVRR spectra of T406 and CPT/T406 show a distinct similarity between the spectra of T406 and dA₂₀ (Figure S10). This is explained by the abundance of adenines in the T406 sequence compared to thymidine and guanosine and so it is expected that the contribution of these nucleotides to the spectra to be larger. Even though the number of adenine nucleotides is equal to the number of cytosines in the sequence (Table S1), the peaks observed are attributed mainly to adenine, due to its higher extinction coefficient at this wavelength and consequently larger Raman enhancement, overshadowing any cytosine bands, which appear at similar wavenumbers. As a result, no significant changes are observed between the spectra of the oligonucleotide and the complex, since any expected changes due to interaction of the polymer with the cytosines cannot be distinguished.

Figure S25. Experimental and calculated absorption (top left axis), stimulated emission (SE) (right axis) and CD (bottom left axis) spectra of T406 and CPT/T406 at 20 °C in PBS buffer with a concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis). For the CPT/ssDNA complexes, the monomeric equivalence between positive and negative charges was achieved. The SE spectra were obtained by subtracting the calculated absorption spectra from the TA spectra at 2 ps after photoexcitation.

S7.1 CPT/T406 temperature stability

Figure S26. Absorption and CD spectra of CPT/T406 in PBS at 20 and 55 °C. Concentration of $7.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ M (monomeric basis).

In Figure S26, the absorption and CD spectra of CPT/T406 at different temperatures show that the shape of the band centred at 522 nm is slightly more structured at 55 °C. The absorbance below 450 nm and above 600 nm is higher for CPT/T406 at 55 °C compared to 20 °C: this is probably due to scattering because the precipitation was much faster at this temperature. The (+/-) CD signal centred at 520 nm is present at both temperatures.

S7.2 Response of polythiophenes with different cationic side chains in complexes with ssDNA

Figure S27. Absorption spectra of (left) P3HT-PMe₃ or (right) P3HT-Im (blue) and its complexes with dA₂₀ (black), dT₂₀ (green) and dC₂₀ (red) in PBS buffer with a concentration of $1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M (monomeric basis) at room temperature.

Figure S28. Graphical comparison of the wavenumbers of C=C symmetric band of P3HT-PMe₃ (blue) or P3HT-Im (magenta) and its complexes with dA₂₀, dC₂₀ and dT₂₀ extracted from the corresponding RR spectra.

Section S8: Excited state properties in CPT/ssDNA complexes

S8.1 Femtosecond Transient absorption

Figure S29. (a) TA excitation wavelengths (400 and 580 nm) noted on the absorption spectra of the three complexes. (b) TA spectra recorded following excitation at 400 nm at selected time delays for CPT/T406.

Figure S29a shows the absorption spectra of the three complexes with the two excitation wavelengths employed in TA experiments. The 400 nm excitation falls into the blue-side of the π - π^* absorption band, while that at 580 nm excites the red-side of the band for CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/T406 and the 0-0 vibronic transition for CPT/dC₂₀. Figure 6a in the main text shows a selection of TA spectra for the CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/dC₂₀ complexes at different time delays following excitation at 400 nm, while Figure S29b shows the respective spectra for CPT/T406. We note that exciting at 580 nm, i.e. more in the red-side of the absorption bands, does not make a significant difference (see Figure S30). For all the complexes, we observe a positive broad band above 800 nm centered at \sim 1050 nm ascribed to the excited state absorption (ESA) of the S1 singlet excited state and a negative feature below 800 nm attributed to ground state bleaching (GSB) and stimulated emission (SE). Within the detection window (up to 1090 nm), the ESA bands have a similar shape for all the complexes. On the other hand, the GSB and SE features present more differences, in agreement with the changes in the stationary spectra due to different degrees of order in CPT. The CPT/dA₂₀ band (top) is broad and centered at around 600 nm, while CPT/dC₂₀ (bottom) has a highly structured band centered at 590 nm with vibronic peaks at 500, 540 (for the GSB), 658 and 730 nm (for the SE). Compared to the results of CPT/dA₂₀, the negative band in

the case of CPT/T406 is slightly more structured and centred at 565 nm, with vibronic peaks at around 520 for the GSB and at 630 and 690 nm for the SE.

Figure S30b shows the normalized TA dynamics for the complexes probed in the exciton band (1000 nm), SE (680 nm) and GSB (510/520 nm). All the decays were globally analysed with a biexponential function and the obtained lifetimes and amplitudes are reported in Table S8. All the TA features decay with a lifetime of a few picoseconds (2.5-4 ps) and a slightly longer one of few tens of picoseconds (22-28 ps). The decays of the excitons and GSB bands mirror each other, meaning that we are probing the same population, which has a comparable lifetime in all complexes. On the other hand, the SE features behave differently for CPT/dA₂₀ and CPT/T406, where the SE decays slower, with a small amplitude decay (31 %) related to τ_1 and a bigger one (69 %) related to τ_2 , while for CPT/dC₂₀, the decay is substantially faster, with 77 % of amplitude decay related to τ_1 (Tables S8-S9). This is in part due to the evolution of the SE spectral shape, as discussed in the main text. These different decay behaviors are reflected in the decay associated amplitude spectra obtained from the global analysis (see Figures S31). Interestingly, the exciton amplitude spectrum of CPT/dC₂₀ changes shape from τ_1 to τ_2 , becoming flatter above 1000 nm (also observed with the 580 nm excitation, see Figure S32). This different shape could be a sign of another species formed in CPT/dC₂₀, such as short-lived polarons or charge transfer excitons.

Figure S30. (a) TA spectra recorded following excitation at 580 nm at selected time delays along with the corresponding stationary absorption (black curves) for the three complexes (top: CPT/dA₂₀, middle: CPT/T406, bottom: CPT/dC₂₀) in solution at 20 °C ($1.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ M on a monomeric unit basis in PBS). (b) Normalized TA dynamics at selected probe wavelengths for the three complexes (dA₂₀, T406, and dC₂₀). Solid lines correspond to the biexponential global fit. The data between ~530 and 620 nm are omitted because of scattering due to the excitation beam.

Table S8: Lifetimes (τ_1 , τ_2) with the associated amplitude percentage (%), offset (y_0) and average lifetime (τ) obtained with a biexponential global fit of selected TA dynamics for CPT/dA₂₀, CPT/T406 and CPT/dC₂₀ following 400 nm excitation.

$\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 400 \text{ nm}$	λ_{probe}	τ_1 (ps)	τ_2 (ps)	y_0	Average τ (ps)
CPT/dA₂₀	1000 nm	3.0 (60%)	22 (40%)	0.02	11
	680 nm	3.0 (31%)	22 (69%)	0.02	16
	530 nm	3.0 (62%)	22 (38%)	-0.04	10
CPT/T406	1000 nm	4.0 (48%)	28 (52%)	0.06	17
	650 nm	4.0 (30%)	28 (70%)	0.00	21
	530 nm	4.0 (48%)	28 (52%)	-0.15	17
CPT/dC₂₀	1000 nm	2.5 (66%)	25 (34%)	0.07	10
	680 nm	2.5 (77%)	25 (23%)	0.06	8
	530 nm	2.5 (63%)	25 (37%)	-0.04	11

Table S9. Lifetimes (τ_1 , τ_2) with the associated amplitude percentage (%), offset (y_0) and average lifetime (τ) obtained with a biexponential global fit of selected TA dynamics for CPT/dA₂₀, CPT/T406 and CPT/dC₂₀ following 580 nm excitation

$\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 580 \text{ nm}$	λ_{probe}	τ_1 (ps)	τ_2 (ps)	y_0	Average τ (ps)
CPT/dA₂₀	1000 nm	2.4 (69%)	37 (31%)	0.05	13
	680 nm	2.4 (72%)	37 (28%)	-0.05	12
	520 nm	2.4 (38%)	37 (62%)	-0.02	24
CPT/T406	1000 nm	5.1 (41%)	37 (59%)	0.02	24
	680 nm	5.1 (51%)	37 (49%)	-0.01	21
	510 nm	5.1 (20%)	37 (80%)	-0.06	30
CPT/dC₂₀	1000 nm	2.6 (55%)	27 (45%)	0.06	14
	680 nm	2.6 (87%)	27 (13%)	0.02	6
	510 nm	2.6 (38%)	27 (62%)	-0.04	18

Tables S8 and S9 contain the values obtained by globally fitting the TA decays of Figure 6a and Figure S30, respectively, with a biexponential model. The behaviour of the excited state after 580 nm excitation is similar to the one observed with the 400 nm excitation: the TA bands decay in an analogous way for all the complexes (τ_1 2.4-5.1 ps, τ_2 27-37 ps), with CPT/T406 slightly slower. Also with this excitation, a fast decay of the SE band is observed for CPT/dC₂₀ with an important amplitude decay with τ_1 (87%) (Figure S32).

Figure S31. Decay-associated amplitude spectra from a biexponential global fit of the TA data following excitation at 400 nm. (top: CPT/dA₂₀, middle: CPT/T406, bottom: CPT/dC₂₀)

Figure S32. Decay-associated amplitude spectra from biexponential global fit of the TA data following excitation at 580 nm. (top: CPT/dA₂₀, middle: CPT/T406, bottom: CPT/dC₂₀)

Section S9: Excited state structural relaxation

S9.1 Resonance Raman Intensity Analysis of CPT/ssDNA in solution

S9.1.1 Determination of Absolute Resonance Raman Cross Sections

Absolute resonance Raman cross sections (σ_R) were determined for all the vibrational modes of CPT in the complexes observed in the RR spectra with excitation at 473 nm. In the case of CPT/dC₂₀ complexes, absolute RR cross sections were also obtained with excitation at 532 nm, which is closer to the absorption maximum due to the red shift of the absorption spectrum (see Figure 2b). In the calculation of the σ_R 's the 801 cm⁻¹ mode of cyclohexane (9.245 M) was used as an external standard. The intensities of the Raman bands were corrected for the spectral response of the instrument using a calibrated tungsten/halogen lamp and for self-absorption according to Equation 2:²⁵

$$\frac{I_{s\text{corrected}}}{I_{r\text{corrected}}} = \frac{I_s c_r (\varepsilon_s + \varepsilon_0)}{I_r c_s (\varepsilon_r + \varepsilon_0)} \quad (2)$$

where c is the concentration of the reference or sample and ε is the extinction coefficient of the sample at the reference or sample peak, or laser line wavelength (subscripts r, s and 0 respectively). The intensities of the Raman bands were determined by deconvolution (see Figure S8), due to spectral congestion, and the area of the Voigt peaks was subsequently calculated.

Absolute RR cross sections as a function of excitation wavelength were determined using Eq. 3 for the most intense bands in the spectra:²⁶

$$\sigma_R(\nu(x)) = \frac{I_{\nu(x)} C_i \left(\frac{1+2\rho}{1+\rho} \right)_{\nu(x)}}{I_i C_{\nu(x)} \left(\frac{1+2\rho}{1+\rho} \right)_i} \sigma_i \quad (3)$$

In Eq. 3, σ_R is the Raman scattering cross section of mode $\nu(x)$, ρ is the depolarization ratio, C is the concentration, and $I_{\nu(x)}$ and I_i are the experimentally determined intensities for the mode of interest and the external standard, respectively. The absolute Raman cross section and depolarization ratio for the 801 cm⁻¹ mode of cyclohexane were previously measured or obtained from an A-term fit to the experimental cross sections ($\sigma_R(473 \text{ nm}) = 1 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2$, $\sigma_R(532 \text{ nm}) = 6.68 \times 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2$, and $\rho = 0.09$. A-term fit parameters: coupling constant $K = 1.3 \times 10^{-9} \text{ \AA}^2$ and $\nu_e = 125000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).²⁶⁻²⁸ The depolarization ratios for the modes of CPT were taken as 1/3.

S9.1.2 Resonance Raman Intensity Analysis (RRIA)

RR band intensities can provide detailed information regarding excited-state structure and dynamics that can be extracted through resonance Raman intensity analysis. As the intensities of RR bands are related to the displacements between the ground and excited state potential energy surface minima in each mode, i.e. the change in molecular structure upon excitation, which in turn determine the shape of the absorption spectrum, simultaneous modelling of the latter and RR excitation profiles (REPs) can provide access to a quantitative picture of the excited state structure. Here, RRIA was employed to provide insights on the significantly different vibronic structures in the absorption spectra of the CPT complexes with dC₂₀, dA₂₀ and T406 oligonucleotides. In our analysis we used expressions from the time-dependent formalism for absorption (Eq. 4) and Resonance Raman scattering (Eq. 5) derived from second order perturbation theory:²⁹

$$\sigma_A(E_L) = \frac{4\pi e^2 E_L M^2}{6\hbar^2 c n} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dE_{00} H(E_{00}) \times \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \langle i | i_1(t) \rangle \exp\left[\frac{i(E_L + \epsilon_i)t}{\hbar}\right] D(t) dt \right] \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{i \rightarrow f}(E_L) = \frac{8\pi e^4 E_S E_L M^4}{9\hbar^6 c^4} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \partial E_{00} H(E_{00}) \left| \int_0^{\infty} \langle f | i_1(t) \rangle \exp\left(\frac{i(E_L + \epsilon_i)t}{\hbar}\right) D(t) dt \right|^2 \quad (5)$$

In the above equations E_S and E_L are the scattered and incident photon energies, respectively (in cm^{-1}), c is the speed of light, and n is the solvent index of refraction. The magnitude of the transition dipole moment for the electronic transition is given by M (in \AA) and ϵ_i is the energy of the initial vibrational state. Γ is the homogeneous line width of the excited state (in cm^{-1}), and is given by the damping function $D(t)$. In this analysis the homogeneous broadening was taken to be Gaussian ($D(t) = e^{-\frac{\Gamma^2 t^2}{\hbar^2}}$). E_{00} is the energy difference between the $\nu = 0$ vibrational state in the ground and excited electronic state and $H(E_{00})$ is the contribution of inhomogeneous broadening, which corresponds to the presence of different solvent sites that are static on the time scale of Raman scattering, thus altering E_{00} . Θ represents the standard deviation of this contribution (in cm^{-1}). The expression $\langle f | i_n(t) \rangle$ represents the time-dependent overlap of the final state in the scattering process with the initial state propagating under the influence of the excited state Hamiltonian in state n . Similarly, the expression $\langle i | i_j(t) \rangle$ in Eq. 4 is the time-dependent overlap of the initial ground vibrational state with the same state propagating on the excited state j potential energy surface.

In the case where both ground and excited states normal coordinates are identical and harmonic, the multidimensional overlaps $\langle i|i(t) \rangle$ and $\langle f|i(t) \rangle$ can be described by one dimensional overlaps in each normal coordinate. Furthermore, in fundamental Raman scattering, where the final state differs from the initial state only in one coordinate, the multidimensional overlaps $\langle f|i(t) \rangle$ can be decomposed into $\langle f|i_1(t) \rangle$ for the Raman active mode and $\langle i|i(t) \rangle$ that refers to all other modes (Eq. 6 and 7).²⁹

$$\langle i|i(t) \rangle = \prod_{k=1}^8 \langle i_k|i_k(t) \rangle \quad (6)$$

$$\langle f|i(t) \rangle = \langle f_1|i_1(t) \rangle \prod_{k=2}^8 \langle i_k|i_k(t) \rangle \quad (7)$$

Here, eight vibrational degrees of freedom are included in the model representing the most intense bands observed in the RR spectra. Explicit expressions have been derived for the one-dimensional overlaps and are available from the literature, where the dependence on the displacement, Δ , between the ground and excited state potential energy surface minima along each coordinate, is apparent ($s = \Delta^2/2$, s : Huang-Rhys parameter):

$$\langle i|i(t) \rangle = \exp \left[-s(1 - e^{-i\omega t}) - \frac{i\omega t}{2} - \frac{iE_0 t}{\hbar} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\langle f|i(t) \rangle = \pm s^{1/2} (e^{-i\omega t} - 1) \langle i|i(t) \rangle \quad (9)$$

The time-dependent overlaps here were calculated using the methodology of Yan and Mukamel,³⁰ using a time step of 0.1 fs for a total of 5000 points.

The stimulated emission spectra were simulated using Eq. 10, which resembles Eq.4, with the difference that now χ are the electronic excited state vibrational eigenfunctions propagated by the ground state Hamiltonian and the inverse Fourier transform is taken.³¹

$$I_{SE}(\omega_L) \propto \sum_{\omega_L} \int_0^\infty \langle \chi|\chi_1(t) \rangle \exp(i(-\omega + \omega_{eg} + \omega_i)t) D(t) dt \quad (10)$$

Table S10. Absolute Resonance Raman cross sections for the major bands in the three complexes.

CPT/dA ₂₀		CPT/T406		CPT/dC ₂₀ excitation at 532 nm	
Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	σ_R (x10 ⁻⁹) (Å ²)	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	σ_R (x10 ⁻⁹) (Å ²)	Frequency (cm ⁻¹)	σ_R (x10 ⁻⁹) (Å ²)
885	0.27±0.07	886	1.39±0.28	885	3.34±1.80
968	1.45±0.41	959	2.30±0.58	977	4.62±2.62
1378	1.19±0.30	1378	3.45±0.96	1376	9.12±5.57
1400	12.24±2.46	1399	18.93±3.61	1394	21.68±10.25
1448	9.09±2.56	1448	6.07±0.63	1448	5.73±1.25
1465	1.87±0.77	1468	4.27±0.38	1463	3.26±1.33
1486	10.78±2.02	1488	10.56±1.62	1484	10.55±4.13
1518	3.98±1.91	1512	3.71±0.30	1510	0.83±0.23

Table S11. Parameters used in the RRIA for the three complexes of CPT.

Transition	ω_g (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_k	ω_g (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_k	ω_g (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_k	ω_g (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_k
	CPT/dC ₂₀ (20°C)			CPT/dC ₂₀ (55°C)			CPT/T406			CPT/dA ₂₀		
ν_1	885	885	0.14	885	885	0.13	885	885	0.12	885	885	0.055
ν_2	977	977	0.17	977	977	0.16	969	969	0.16	968	968	0.125
ν_3	1376	1376	0.56	1376	1376	0.54	1378	1378	0.38	1378	1378	0.31
ν_4	1394	1394	0.93	1394	1394	0.94	1399	1399	0.97	1400	1400	1.11
ν_5	1448	1448	0.40	1448	1448	0.35	1448	1448	0.59	1448	1448	1.00
ν_6	1463	1463	0.25	1463	1463	0.23	1468	1468	0.46	1465	1465	0.48
ν_7	1484	1484	0.38	1484	1484	0.33	1488	1487	0.70	1486	1486	1.11
ν_8	1510	1510	0.11	1510	1510	0.09	1512	1512	0.40	1518	1518	0.60
Γ (cm ⁻¹)		45			45			85			100	
Θ (cm ⁻¹)		480			450			755			900	
E_{00} (cm ⁻¹)		16875			16900			17900			16650	
M (Å)		0.822			0.87			0.881			0.975	

The parameters used in the modelling (Table S10-S11) include the ground and excited state frequencies (ω_g and ω_e) and the displacements (Δ) along each normal coordinate, the electronic

transition dipole moment (M), the homogeneous (Γ) and inhomogeneous broadening (Θ) and the difference between the $v = 0$ in the ground and excited electronic states (E_{00}).

A good fit was obtained for the red edge of the absorption spectra of the complexes (Figure 2 in main manuscript and S25 above), with a corresponding excellent fit to the REPs of all the prominent bands in the RR spectra of the polymer (Figure S33-35). Higher electronic transitions to higher singlet states or due to more disordered polymer populations) were not included in the calculation, explaining the deviation from the blue side of the experimental absorption bands, which however did not affect the calculation of the REPs. Even though we choose to simplify the model used in this study, the parameters obtained still provide a self-consistent comparative picture of the conformational changes occurring in the three complexes.

As described in the main manuscript, we find an overall larger conformational rearrangement in the excited state in the complexes where the polymer is less tightly bound to the DNA strand and more torsionally disordered, with a three times larger structural evolution on going from the ground to the excited state in the case of dA₂₀ (reorganization energy, $\lambda = 1119 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for dC₂₀, 1627 cm^{-1} for T406 and 3024 cm^{-1} for dA₂₀, see Figure 7a).

The calculation of absolute resonance Raman cross sections (σ_R) allows the distinction between the contributions of homogeneous and inhomogeneous broadening through RRIA, as the σ_R depends differently on the broadening terms than then absorption cross section. Specifically, in the equation for the σ_R the homogeneous broadening appears as damping at the amplitude level, while inhomogeneous broadening produces a distribution of transition energies at the probability level (see Equations 4 and 5).²⁸ We find that the inhomogeneous broadening doubles from 450 cm^{-1} (56 meV) to 900 cm^{-1} (112 meV) as we go from CPT/dC₂₀ to CPT/dA₂₀, indicating the larger number of energetic sites available due to conformational disorder. We observed that the homogeneous broadening increases from 45 cm^{-1} to 100 cm^{-1} , which corresponds to a decrease in total dephasing from 118 to 53 fs. Since Γ includes contributions from excited state lifetime and pure dephasing, one can use the exciton lifetime determined from the TA measurements to calculate the contribution from pure dephasing. The average lifetime is on the order of 15 ps, therefore pure dephasing (e.g. due to collisions with the solvent) seems to play the dominant role in the excited state reactivity.

Figure S33. Calculated Raman excitation profiles (REPs) for the most prominent vibrational modes of CPT/dC₂₀ complex. The points with error bars denote the experimentally calculated absolute RR cross sections at 532 nm.

Figure S34. Calculated Raman excitation profiles (REPs) for the most prominent vibrational modes of CPT/dA₂₀ complex. The points with error bars denote the experimentally calculated absolute RR cross sections at 473 nm.

Figure S35. Calculated Raman excitation profiles (REPs) for the most prominent vibrational modes of CPT/T406 complex. The points with error bars denote the experimentally calculated absolute RR cross sections at 473 nm.

Figure S36. Experimental and calculated stimulated emission spectra for CPT/dC₂₀ at selected time delays.

In order to obtain the experimental spectrum of the SE, the calculated absorption spectrum of the complex was used for the subtraction of the GSB band from the negative TA feature for each time delay (adjusted in order to match the intensity of the GSB), since this exemplified transition to a single state, rather than the multiple transitions represented from the experimental absorption spectrum that led to oversubtraction artefacts. The remaining part corresponding to the SE was

described very well by the simulation (Figure 7c, Figure S36 and Table S12). The 2 ps spectra were chosen to appear in Figure 2 in the main text in order to have representative “relaxed” TA spectra and avoid the ultrafast phenomena happening within the first picoseconds.

Table S12. Parameters used in the stimulated emission fitting of the complex CPT/dC₂₀ for different time delays.

Transition	ω_g (cm ⁻¹)	ω_e (cm ⁻¹)	Δ_k				
			0.2 ps	1.05 ps	2 ps	5 ps	10 ps
ν_1	885	885	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.23
ν_2	977	977	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16
ν_3	1376	1376	0.54	0.54	0.54	0.48	0.24
ν_4	1394	1394	0.93	0.68	0.80	0.63	0.53
ν_5	1448	1448	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.25
ν_6	1463	1463	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23
ν_7	1484	1484	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.30
ν_8	1510	1510	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Γ (cm ⁻¹)			45	45	45	45	45
Θ (cm ⁻¹)			450	425	415	415	415
E_{00} (cm ⁻¹)			16480	16440	16360	16360	16300
M (Å)			0.513	0.475	0.430	0.320	0.218

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